

Design of Scalable Filterless Horseshoe-and-Spur Networks with Coherent Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers

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Abstract: This paper proposes a scalable filterless horseshoe-and-spur architecture optimized using a novel and exact integer linear programming (ILP) framework. The proposed solution allows network expansion with minimal disruptions and less cost compared to simple horseshoes.

1. Introduction

Next-generation networking solutions and technologies must let operators choose the best options for their variable growing needs. Cost-effectiveness and scalability are among the most crucial factors in metro-aggregation networks. These networks require a distinct transmission approach due to their growing capacity demands and strict up-time requirements. Horseshoe and ring topologies have been dominant in this space because they offer resilience against single-point failure and effectively handle the hub-and-spoke traffic patterns of these segments [1]. Recent research suggests a significant cost reduction for metro-aggregation networks by employing coherent point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transmission technology alongside the possibility of carrying out optical aggregation – enabled by digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) [2] – instead of electrical aggregation while also minimizing or eliminating the use of active switches via a filterless architecture [3].

An important design principle is that both the topology and the underlying architecture must be able to accommodate the increasing traffic demands at existing or new sites. Previous studies have demonstrated that DSCM-based P2MP transceivers offer a significant advantage for long-term traffic growth [4,5]. This is achieved by introducing higher capacity transceiver generations and the ability to rearrange devices as needed. In addition, the capacity per node can be increased or decreased by dynamically changing subcarrier (SC) assignment, e.g., via a software-defined network controller. Still, when the capacity demand increases, it might be necessary to deploy more than one transceiver at certain nodes. Upgrading optimized horseshoe filterless networks with new leaf nodes, however, presents a unique challenge. Unlike traditional networks, the addition of a single node in a filterless network can impact all communication links due to the absence of filters and regenerators [3]. This can be compounded by the inherent tight margins in highly optimized networks at their initial deployment [6]. Two primary scaling strategies can be considered: 1) adding parallel horseshoes that share hub nodes and 2) extending the existing horseshoe with spur-like branches [5]. Although adding horseshoes offers a significant capacity increase, it requires a substantial upfront investment to connect the hubs. On the other hand, deploying branches requires careful planning to avoid service disruption due to changes in network performance.

In this paper, we propose a cost-effective and scalable horseshoe-and-spur architecture designed to accommodate in the long term (under the uncertainties involved) and with minimum disruption: 1) more leaf nodes / transceivers (in different geographical places), or 2) more P2MP transceivers per leaf node. We introduce an exact integer linear programming (ILP) optimization framework specifically modified for this architecture. We compare it with simple horseshoe architecture and analyze possible upgrade scenarios.

2. Network Architecture

The design of the nodes is critical in optical filterless networks. It impacts optical signals, e.g., by determining how much power is lost due to passive devices in each transmission path. We modify our previously proposed architecture [3] by using simple 2-by-2 couplers for express and add/drop functionality at leaf/transit nodes. As shown in

Fig. 1, the nodes must deliver optical signals downstream and upstream for the branches. We use a splitter/combiner to aggregate or distribute signals to and from the main horseshoe fibers. Branches can have one or more leaf nodes, arranged either in a single or multi-stage tree structure. Optical amplifiers can be strategically placed at two key points: before transit nodes and at the add/drop points of transit nodes. Additionally, booster amplifiers can be used at hub nodes to amplify the signal before it is distributed downstream, while pre-amplifiers can be used to amplify the signal at the input of the hub nodes. Note that the node architecture for both transmission directions is now a coupled (in contrast to our original ILP [3]) problem in this case and must be optimized jointly.

Fig. 1: Proposed horseshoe-and-spur architecture.

Instead of optimizing the whole architecture, we consider a power budget value for branches similar to passive optical networks (PONs) planning approach [7]. The key benefit of this method is that it allows for easier upgrades in the uncertain future by letting operators focus solely on the power budget assigned to each branch and expand their network without compromising the availability or performance of the rest of the network.

3. Optimization Framework

We leverage ILP to create an optimization framework that guarantees optimal solutions. We present only the main input parameters, variables, and constraints due to the lack of space.

Input Parameters

- L List of transit nodes
- A List of fiber links attenuation
- G_g EDFA gain range, 0 implies no amplifier
- P_l Launch power per SC
- P_n Nonlinearity power threshold per SC
- P_s Transceivers power sensitivity per SC
- P_x SCs power difference tolerance
- P_b^l Power budget for branch l
- H_s^p Add/drop and express loss of device s

Decision Variables

- $\Delta_{l,t}^s$: Binary variable for coupler selection; 1 if coupler s is selected for leaf l in direction t , otherwise 0
- $\gamma_{l,t}^p$: port p loss of coupler in leaf l in direction t
- $\mu_{a,g}^{12}, \mu_{a,g}^{21}$: Binary variable; 1 if amplifier on link a takes gain g for direction 12 and 21, otherwise 0
- $\mu_{l,g}^{d1}, \mu_{l,g}^{d2}$: Binary variables; 1 if drop amplifiers at leaf l takes gain g , otherwise 0
- $\mu_{l,g}^{u1}, \mu_{l,g}^{u2}$: Binary variables; 1 if the add amplifiers at leaf l takes the gain g , otherwise 0

- μ_g^{b1} / μ_g^{b2} : Binary variables; 1 if the booster amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0
- μ_g^{p1} / μ_g^{p2} : Binary variable; 1 if the pre-amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0
- $\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{12}, \varepsilon_{21}, \varepsilon_{22}$: Lower and upper bounds of power from transit to hub nodes

Equation (1) expresses the objective function of the ILP model and consists of two sub-goals:

$$z = N_l + w[\varepsilon_{12} - \varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22} - \varepsilon_{21}] \quad (1)$$

where w is a small weighting factor that ensures the second goal has lower priority. N_l is the total number of amplifiers deployed. The second term of the objective function is the sum of the maximum SCs power difference at the hubs' receivers.

$$\sum_g \mu_{Xg}^{WZ} = 1, \quad \forall a \in A \quad \text{or} \quad l \in L \quad (2)$$

Constraints (2) select a gain for all amplifiers in the network (Xg and WZ have to be replaced with appropriate indices for each amplifier).

$$\sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s = 1 \quad \forall l \in L, t \in \{12, 21\} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_{l,t}^p = \sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s H_s^p \quad \forall l, t, p \quad (4)$$

Constraints (3) are used to choose the couplers and splitters/combiners ratios at each transit node. Besides, constraints (4) assign the resulting loss to each port of the couplers and $T_{i,j}^l$, representing transit plus add/drop losses (transit nodes can be seen as a six-port passive device), can be calculated.

$$-T_{15}^l + P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^d G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} T_{12}^{lx} N_d^{l,lx} \geq P_s + P_b \quad \forall l \in L \quad (5)$$

$$-T_{62}^l + P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^u G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_u^{l,a} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} T_{12}^{lx} N_u^{l,lx} \geq P_s + P_b \quad \forall l \in L \quad (6)$$

$$-T_{45}^l + P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^d G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_u^{l,a} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} T_{43}^{lx} N_u^{l,lx} \geq P_s + P_b \quad \forall l \in L \quad (7)$$

$$-T_{63}^l + P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^u G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_d^{l,a} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} T_{43}^{lx} N_d^{l,lx} \geq P_s + P_b \quad \forall l \in L \quad (8)$$

Constraints (5) to (8) calculate the power received by transceivers in downstream and upstream directions and they have to meet the defined power budget and sensitivity of the transceivers. Note that T_{ij}^l characterizes transit nodes' losses and is a function of $\gamma_{l,t}^p$.

$$\varepsilon_{11} - \varepsilon_{12} \leq P_x, \quad \varepsilon_{21} - \varepsilon_{22} \leq P_x, \quad (9)$$

Constraint (9) ensures that the difference between the highest and lowest SCs power levels does not exceed the threshold defined for each transceiver located at the hub nodes under the condition that the signals coming from branches been already equalized before entering the horseshoe by the means of variable launch power, attenuators or gain control circuits [2]. The rest of the constraints are used to guarantee that the power per SC does not exceed the preset nonlinear power threshold in critical points across the horseshoe (see similar constraints (10) and (11) of Ref [3]).

4. Results

We consider coherent P2MP transceivers using DP 16-QAM modulation, requiring a minimum received power of -24 dBm per SC. The maximum transceiver output power is $P_t = -12$ dBm per SC. To have negligible nonlinear interference, the power per SC has to be less than $P_n = -8$ dBm across the length of every span. Single-mode fiber with a 0.22 dB/km loss coefficient is considered, along with passive devices introducing an additional 0.5 dB excess loss. Importantly, the power difference between SCs at the hub receivers must not exceed 8 dB (denoted by P_x) [8]. We assume that amplifier gain can be between 6 and 20 dB with 1 dB increments. We utilize the statistical properties of real-life horseshoes from Ref [9] (13.2 km average link length) to generate 10 synthetic 8-branch horseshoes (or 8-leaf simple horseshoes) with similar characteristics. A maximum of 16 express, 16 add/drop, and 4 booster/pre, totaling 36 amplifiers, can be deployed. The optimization framework is implemented using the JuMP package [10] and the CPLEX solver.

Fig. 2: Optimized average number of amplifiers for simple horseshoe, and proposed horseshoe-and-spur architectures (90% confidence intervals indicated as error bars).

Fig. 2 shows the average number of amplifiers for the simple horseshoe architecture and horseshoe-and-spur architecture with 6 dB and 12 dB power budgets while considering different coupler ratios. "50:50", and "70:30 & 90:10" indicate that 50/50 or 70:30 and 90:10 ratios are considered for the splitters/combiners, respectively. Scenario "All" assumes the availability of all ratios from 10% to 90% with 10% granularity. The average number of amplifiers varies from 6.8 to 9.5 for different coupler scenarios for the simple horseshoe. The flexibility in coupler ratios deployed provides solutions with fewer amplifiers for horseshoe-and-spur architecture as well. However, the amplifier count is approximately 40% to 85% larger when considering the need to support fixed 6 dB and 12 dB expansion power budgets compared to simple horseshoes. Let us consider a simple example: a single-stage tree with four leaf nodes at the end and a maximum distance of 10 km from the transit node. This type of setup typically requires a power budget of around 10-12 dB. Hence, the horseshoe-and-spur design is much more efficient than the simple horseshoe needing only about a third as many amplifiers per leaf node (0.27 vs 0.93) for the "70:30 & 90:10" scenario.

Filterless networks are generally more cost-effective than using reconfigurable add/drop multiplexers (ROADMs). However, they offer less flexibility in reconfiguration [11]. We investigate three upgrade scenarios – as reported in Fig. 3 – when increasing the power budget from 6 dB to 12 dB: 1) passive devices are fixed. Amplifiers can be re-optimized, 2) existing amplifiers remain in place but passive devices can be reconfigured, and 3) both existing amplifiers location and the network layout (node architecture) are fixed. New amplifiers can be added.

We simulate these scenarios by running the ILP twice, using the first run's output to fix the necessary parameters for the second. As shown in Fig. 3, for the "70:30 & 90:10" coupler scenario, more amplifiers are needed compared to a scenario where the entire network can be reconfigured (one-shot planning shown by the dashed line). Specifically, when passive devices are fixed, the number of amplifiers increases to an average of 17.7, compared to 15.9 amplifiers when deployed amplifiers cannot be relocated. The composition of amplifiers is different. For instance, the "Fixed amplifiers" scenario requires more express amplifiers. The final scenario offers the least flexibility and requires over

Fig. 3: Optimized average number of amplifiers when upgrading power budget from 6 dB to 12 dB.

50% more amplifiers than a design that allows full reconfiguration (but likely with higher OpEx and disruption). As a result, filterless horseshoe-and-spur architecture with P2MP transceivers can provide more flexibility if spending more upfront and considering a high power budget. However, it is important to consider other factors like network dynamics, and availability constraints.

5. Conclusions

We demonstrated that the proposed horseshoe-and-spur filterless architecture utilizing P2MP transceivers can potentially host more leaf nodes cost-effectively over time with minimal disruption compared to a traditional design since the spurs upgrade become decoupled from the design.

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